

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN ULTRASONIC METHODS FOR METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a recently developed nondestructive approach for characterizing advanced composite materials will be presented. This new methodology uses ultrasonic waves to characterize the fiber-matrix interface based on the shear wave back reflectivity (SBR) and normal incidence longitudinal wave interrogation techniques and enables evaluation of composite consolidation and characterization of the interfacial elastic properties at a localized level. This approach is nondestructive in nature in contrast to traditional destructive characterization techniques which are tedious and render the samples unusable for other experiments. Further, novel methodologies for imaging nondestructively the fiber microcracking and the interface failure have been developed. The nondestructive imaging of failure modes in composites can provide critical information to materials researchers for micro-mechanics modeling studies to evaluate fracture and fatigue behavior of composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The characterization of the interface is of great interest to the researchers who are developing new composite systems. In order to determine the optimum interface properties, a model monofilament composite is usually used which has an interface with tailored properties depending on the choice of the fiber and the matrix materials, the fiber coating and the processing conditions. Many investigators have employed a number of experimental destructive techniques including fiber push-out, fiber fragmentation, transverse loading tests, etc. to characterize the interface in model composites. In this paper, the recent development of novel nondestructive techniques for (a) the evaluation of the consolidation in composites, (b) the monitoring of the fiber fracture during the fragmentation test, (c) the evaluation of interface failure during the transverse test, and (d) the evaluation of the elastic properties of the fiber-matrix interface, will be presented

2 EVALUATION OF CONSOLIDATION OF COMPOSITES

An ultrasonic nondestructive evaluation methodology of consolidation and microstructure characterization of advanced composites has been developed to aid the design and fabrication of composites so that the processing parameters can be suitably adjusted to obtain complete densification around the fibers in both MMC and CMC as well as desired microstructure of metallic matrices. In addition, the methodology can be used to ensure that the composite panels are devoid of any global problems such as fiber movement, ply delamination, and manufacturing anomalies such as voids. Post processing NDE is essential before interfacial characterization is performed.

2.1 PROCESSING OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES

Composites based on reactive matrices with high melting temperatures such as titanium alloys which are usually processed by solid state diffusion bonding of matrix foils, powders, or sprayed deposits with reinforcements. For example, the processing of continuously reinforced titanium matrix composites by the foil-fiber-foil method typically involves diffusion bonding of rolled matrix alloy foils with reinforcing fibers in the form of woven mats with a cross-weave to hold the fibers in place [1]. The processing conditions are carefully selected in order to achieve complete consolidation and produce acceptable composite material. In practice, the initial processing temperatures are chosen on the basis of known flow characteristics of the matrix alloy at different temperatures and strain rates, and the consolidation of these samples is checked by metallographic examination of polished sections. However, the use of metallography alone is generally inadequate since consolidation often occurs nonuniformly within the composite panels [1].

2.2 ULTRASONIC CHARACTERIZATION

The samples made as described above were ultrasonically imaged using two different techniques: (1) Shear wave interrogation and (2) Longitudinal wave interrogation. In the shear wave technique, a 25 MHz focused transducer (6.3 mm diameter, 12.7 mm focal length) was used in the pulse-echo mode. The ultrasonic wave front was incident on the specimen surface inclined to the vertical plane at an angle between the first and the second critical angles which are defined as the angles of incidence above which longitudinal and shear waves, respectively, will not propagate in the matrix material. As a result, only vertically polarized shear waves propagated in the matrix with a refraction angle ' θ_S ' (given by the Snell's law) and were incident on the fiber/matrix interface.

The ultrasonic image of fibers with different degree of consolidation depends on the angle of incidence of the beam and the shape of the cross-section of the poor consolidation area. The reflected amplitude is maximum at the center of the fiber (which is a cylindrical reflector) and is gradually reduced as the transducer is scanning away from the center of the fiber. In the case of shear wave interrogation of a fiber with poor consolidation, the embedded reflector in the matrix is non cylindrical in shape, therefore, the wave will be reflected away from the receiver and only a small part of the energy (which is incident on the region close to the top of the fiber) will come back to the transducer thereby distorting the ultrasonic image of the fiber. Consequently, the image of the fiber will appear with a smaller diameter compared to a well consolidated fiber, and also the reflected ultrasonic amplitude will be lower (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Ultrasonic images from Ti-14Al-21Nb/SiC single fiber composite (Panel B) using shear wave interrogation with different angles of wave front incidence: (a) 18° and (b) 24° .

Figure 2 Ultrasonic image from Ti-14Al-21Nb/SiC single fiber composite (Panel B) using longitudinal wave interrogation. AA', BB', and CC' indicate sections at which metallographic samples were examined. The ultrasonic images were corroborated with metallography (Figure 3).

In the case of normal incidence longitudinal wave interrogation, and when a well consolidated fiber is imaged, very small amount of signal will be reflected back to the transducer and the fiber will be barely visible. However, when a situation similar to the configuration in Figure 1 is presented, higher amplitude of the signal will be reflected back to the transducer and the image of the fiber will be as shown in the Fig. 2. The corresponding metallographs are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Optical micrographs of vacuum hot pressed Ti-14Al-21Nb/SiC (Panel B) sample showing poor consolidation at sections (a) AA' (b) BB', and (c) CC'.

3 NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF THE FIBER FRAGMENTATION PHENOMENON

In this section the novel technique of nondestructive imaging of fiber fracture is presented.

3.1 BACKGROUND

In the fiber fragmentation test, a composite sample made of a single fiber embedded in a ductile matrix is subjected to tensile loading along the fiber axis [2-6]. When the tensile stress, which is transferred from the matrix to the fiber by shear, exceeds the local fiber strength, the single fiber breaks successively into smaller fragments until the fragments become too short to enable further increase in stress level. Using arguments based on shear lag analysis, Kelly and Tyson [2] showed that the critical length of fiber for load transfer, L_c , is a function of the interfacial shear stress according to the equation

$$\tau_i = \sigma_f \frac{d}{2L_c} \quad (1)$$

where τ_i is the shear stress, σ_f is the tensile strength of the fiber of critical length, L_c , and d is the fiber diameter. As a result, the measurement of fiber fragment size is critical to the understanding

of the load transfer behavior of the fiber-matrix interface. However, the metallographic approach to measure the fiber fragment size might induce further damage and, therefore, a nondestructive method of imaging would improve the reliability of the measurement of the lengths of the fragments of the embedded fiber. A nondestructive ultrasonic approach developed [8,9] to image the fragmented fiber embedded in the matrix is presented here.

3.2 ULTRASONIC EVALUATION

The SBR technique was used to image fiber fragments in model composite specimens used for fiber fragmentation testing which consisted of a SCS-6 SiC fiber embedded in Ti-6Al-4V or Ti-14Al-21Nb (wt.%) matrix alloys. A 25 MHz focused wave was used in the pulse-echo mode for the imaging of the embedded fiber in a sample before and after the fragmentation test. The ultrasonic wave front was incident on the composite at an angle of 24°. The transducer was positioned such that the wave front was defocused (-1.5 mm) from the surface of the sample and the focal plane of the incident beam was at the back-surface of the fiber. Back-reflected ultrasound was gated for imaging. Figure 4 shows the images of a SiC fiber in an untested composite along with the images of fragmented fiber in Ti-6Al-4V/SiC and Ti-14Al-21Nb/SiC composites. This figure also shows that the SBR imaging patterns observed corroborate well with the results of metallography. In addition to imaging the fractured fibers, the SBR technique can be used to characterize the extent of matrix consolidation around the fibers. This methodology can also be used to detect any global defects in composite panels such as fiber swimming, ply delamination and voids.

4 NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF THE TRANSVERSE TEST

This section presents a new methodology to assess the interfacial stress at fracture.

4.1 BACKGROUND

The newly developed method is based on an ultrasonic NDE technique which is used in-situ to monitor the deformation and failure of the fiber-matrix interface under transverse loading. The transverse test which is used to study the interface fracture behavior is usually performed using single fiber model composites. Single fiber specimens are well suited for interface evaluation because, (a) the interface chemical bonding, which depends on the chemical reaction between the matrix and the fiber materials during processing, remains the same in a single fiber sample as well as in a multi-ply composite panel, and (b) the residual stresses at the interface are relatively easy to calculate in the single fiber sample, thereby making it feasible to account for the residual stresses in the modeling of the test to derive more accurate conclusions about the stress at fracture of the fiber-matrix interface. Monofilament composite samples for these experiments were processed by the foil-fiber-foil technique. After processing of the single fiber composite samples, the samples are cut into dog-bone-shaped specimens with the fiber axis perpendicular to the loading axis of the samples as shown in Figure 5.

4.2 ULTRASONIC EVALUATION

Transverse tensile tests were carried out using a micro-straining stage (Figure 6) built in the WL/Materials Directorate [6]: The loading was applied stepwise so that the ultrasonic scanning could be done in-situ under the loaded condition at different stress levels. An in-situ ultrasonic nondestructive technique was used for this purpose.

The damage of the fiber-matrix interface during the transverse test was evaluated using the shear-wave back reflectivity technique (SBR) [5, 7]. The loading of the samples was done in incremental steps. At each step of loading the fiber-matrix interface was ultrasonically imaged (while holding the sample under that load). Figure 7 shows the stress-strain diagram for the tensile test of a Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6 single fiber composite sample under transverse loading, and the corresponding ultrasonic shear wave images at various stress levels of the sample labeled 'A through 'K' in the figure. The image labeled 'A' in Figure 7 corresponds to the fiber-matrix interface before the commencement of the mechanical loading of the sample. Reflectivity image 'B' indicates the first

few points of interface that fracture at about 350 MPa (shown with the maximum amplitude calibrated to red in the color scale but visible as black in Figure 7 due to black and white reproduction of color). These points of interface fracture are located near the two ends of the fiber and in several places at the center of the fiber. The reflectivity images 'C' through 'J' show the progression of interfacial damage as the load increases. The image 'K' shows that the entire interface has been fractured at about 700 MPa. An important conclusion drawn from using in-situ SBR imaging of the transverse test contradicts a commonly accepted assumption that the entire interface is likely to fracture almost instantaneously once a sufficiently high stress level is reached because of the existence of a weak diffusion bond (as contrasted to mechanical bonding).

Figure 4 (a) Ultrasonic image of an untested single fiber sample. (b) Fiber fragmentation image in a Ti-6Al-4V sample with an SCS-6 Fiber. (c) Fiber fragmentation image in a Ti-14Al-21Nb (Ti-24Al-11Nb, atomic %) sample with an SCS-6 Fiber. (d) Corroboration of the ultrasonic imaging of fiber fragmentation with metallography. (e) SEM image of the fragmented fiber showing secondary fractures in addition to the primary fracture.

Figure 5 Experimental Configuration Showing Transverse Orientation of the Fiber in a Sample and the Direction of Loading.

Figure 6 Configuration of the Micro-Straining Stage for Ultrasonic In-Situ Imaging Arrangement.

5 CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERFACIAL ELASTIC PROPERTY

5.1 ANALYTICAL MODEL

An analytical modeling has been developed for the microscopic evaluation of the elastic properties of the fiber-matrix interface. This model is necessary for the selection of various experimental parameters such as the frequency of ultrasound and angle of incidence and provides the relationship which is necessary to interpret the future experimental results. The theoretical model considers the reflection of an ultrasonic wave front from a single fiber embedded in a homogeneous isotropic matrix. Although the analysis of the ultrasonic technique is developed for a monofilament composite, the method is equally applicable to study the fiber-matrix interface in the outermost layers of a real, multi-fiber composite system. The ultrasonic characterization of the interface is achieved by the analysis of the back-reflected shear wave signal [5] from the fiber-matrix interface. Figure 8 shows the configuration of the problem.

The interface between the matrix and the fiber is modeled by: (i) assuming continuity of normal and shear stresses and normal displacements at the interface, and (ii) by allowing the discontinuity of shear displacements at the interface. It is assumed that the vibration is transmitted instantaneously from one medium to the other by weightless springs with an equivalent rigidity of N_S [GPa/ μm] which represents the interfacial stiffness. From the model the back-reflection coefficient of shear waves is dependent on the properties of the matrix, the properties of the fiber, the diameter of the fiber, the angle of incidence, the ultrasonic frequency of interrogation, and the interfacial stiffness coefficient N_S .

5.2 ULTRASONIC EVALUATION

The experimental procedure for the determination of the shear stiffness coefficient of the fiber/matrix interface consists of (a) measuring the shear wave back reflection coefficient of the interface and, (b) inverting the calculation of the shear stiffness coefficient by using the relationship

between N_S and back-reflection coefficient established by the theoretical modeling for an appropriate ultrasonic frequency of interrogation.

Figure 7 In-Situ Ultrasonic SBR Imaging of an Embedded SCS-6 Fiber in Ti-6Al-4V Matrix During Various Stages of Transverse Loading.

Figure 8 Geometry of the problem

For the measurement of the interface elastic property, first, a reference A-scan was obtained. A Fourier transformation of that reference A-scan provided the incident magnitude at 25 MHz. Similarly, A-scans were obtained from two samples, one containing a hole (simulated debond) and another with an embedded fiber. The corresponding reflected magnitudes at 25 MHz were measured using Fourier transformation and the reflection coefficient was calculated. The calculated reflection coefficient was used to inverse calculate the shear stiffness coefficient of the equivalent elastic interface using the theoretical curve. The values are listed in Table 1. It should be noted that the shear stiffness coefficient for the hole was zero (Table 1) as expected (because the hole simulates a debond). The fiber-matrix interface and the hole in the matrix were imaged (Figure 9) to show the sensitivity of the reflected ultrasonic amplitude to the variability of the interface properties. The line plots in Figure 9 clearly demonstrate the sensitivity of the technique to the variability of the interfacial property.

Figure 9 (a) Ultrasonic back-reflected amplitude image of an SCS-6 fiber embedded in Ti-6Al-4V matrix showing varying interfacial property compared to the image from a hole of the same diameter as that of the fiber. (b) Line plots of the reflected amplitudes along the lengths of the fiber and the hole, respectively, showing the variability of the reflected amplitude from the fiber-matrix interface.

Table I Theoretically calculated shear stiffness coefficient based on experimentally measured back-reflection coefficient.

Material	Reflection Coefficient	Shear Stiffness Coefficient (GPa/ μm)
Hole	0.246	0.0
Ti-6Al-4V	0.082	9.4
Ti-24Al-11Nb	0.096	7.3

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